

PANJARADA UCH ZARACHALI SISTEMANING XOS QIYMATLARI HAQIDA

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Ushbu ishda uch o‘lchamli \mathbb{Z}^3 panjarada juft-jufti bilan o‘zaro kontakt $\mu > 0$ va $\lambda > 0$ potensial yordamida ta’sirlashuvchi ixtiyoriy uchta (ikkitasi massasi 1 bo‘lgan bozon va bittasi massasi $m = 1/\gamma < 1$ bo‘lgan boshqa zarracha) zarrachali sistemaga mos Shryodinger operatori $H_{\mu,\lambda,\gamma}(K)$, $K \in \mathbb{T}^3$, qaraladi. Massalar nisbatining $\gamma = \gamma_1$ kritik qiymati mavjud bo‘lib, yetarlicha katta μ larda va mahkamlangan $\lambda > 0$ uchun $\gamma \in (0, \gamma_1)$ bo‘lganda $H_{\mu,\lambda,\gamma}(\pi)$, $\pi = (\pi, \pi, \pi)$ operator muhim spektrning chap tomonida kamida bitta xos qiymatga, $\gamma \in (\gamma_1, +\infty)$ bo‘lganda esa kamida to‘rtta xos qiymatga ega ekanligi isbotlanadi.

[1] ishda juft-jufti bilan tortishish kontakt potentsiallar yordamida o‘zaro ta’sir qiluvchi uchta zarrachali (ulardan ikkitasi-bozonlar, uchinchisi-ixtiyoriy) sistema qaralgan. Bu sistemaga mos uch zarrachali $H_{\mu,\lambda,\gamma}(K)$ operatorning muhim spektri tavsiflangan. Uchta zarrachaning yo ikkita, yoki uchta ikki zarrachali qism sistemalari uch zarrachali muhim spektr chap chetida virtual sathlarga ega bo‘lgan hollarda (ya’ni $\mu_1 = \mu_1^0$ va $\mu_2 \in [0, \mu_2^0]$ yoki $\mu_\alpha = \mu_\alpha^0$, $\alpha = 1, 3$ bo‘lganda) efimov effekti mavjudligi isbotlangan.

$H_{\mu,\lambda,\gamma}(\pi)$ operator muhim spektrining $[\tau_{min,\gamma}(\mu, \pi), \tau_{max,\gamma}(\mu, \pi)]$ “ikki zarrachali shoxchasi” dan biri $\mu \rightarrow +\infty$, da $-\infty$ ga intiladi, natijada operatorning xos qiymatlari muhim spektri bilan “yutiladi”. Shuning uchun tabiiy savol tug‘iladi: yetarlicha katta $\mu > 0$ va tayinlangan $\lambda > 0$ da muhim spektrdan chapda yotgan $H_{\mu,\lambda,\gamma}(\pi)$ operatorning xos qiymatlari mavjudmi va agar mavjud bo‘lsa, ular nechta?

Ushbu ishda massalar nisbatlarining shunday $\gamma_1 \approx 4,7655$ kritik qiymati mavjudki ixtiyoriy $\lambda > 0$ va $\gamma \in (0, \gamma_1)$ da $H_{\mu,\lambda,\gamma}(\pi)$ operator hech bo‘lmaganda bitta xos qiymatga ega, $\gamma > \gamma_1$ da esa $\mu > 0$ ning yetarlicha katta qiymatlarida muhim spektrdan chapda yotgan to‘rttadan kam bo‘lmagan xos qiymatga ega bo‘lishi isbotlangan.

Faraz qilaylik, $\mathbb{T}^3 = (-\pi, \pi]^3$ uch o'lchamli tor, hamda $L_2[(\mathbb{T}^3)^d]$, $d = 1, 2 - (\mathbb{T}^3)^d$ da aniqlangan kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi funksiyalarning Gilbert fazosi bo'lsin. $L_2[(\mathbb{T}^3)^2]$ –fazoning simmetrik funksiyalaridan tashkil topgan qism fazoni quyidagicha belgilaymiz:

$$L_2^{sym}[(\mathbb{T}^3)^2] = \{f \in L_2[(\mathbb{T}^3)^2]: f(p, q) = f(q, p)\}.$$

Uch zarrachali sistema energiyasiga mos diskret Shryodinger $H_{\mu, \lambda, \gamma}(K)$, $K \in \mathbb{T}^3$ operator $L_2^{sym}[(\mathbb{T}^3)^2]$ Gilbert fazosida quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$H_{\mu, \lambda, \gamma}(K) = H_{0, \gamma}(K) - \mu(V_1 + V_2) - \lambda V_3, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda

$$\begin{aligned} (H_{0, \gamma}(K)f)(p, q) &= E_{K, \gamma}(p, q)f(p, q), \\ E_{K, \gamma}(p, q) &= \varepsilon(p) + \varepsilon(q) + \gamma\varepsilon(K - p - q), \\ \varepsilon(p) &= 3 - \xi(p), \quad \xi(p) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \cos p_i, \quad p = (p_1, p_2, p_3) \in \mathbb{T}^3 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$(V_1 f)(p, q) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} f(p, s) ds, \quad (V_2 f)(p, q) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} f(s, q) ds,$$

$$(V_3 f)(p, q) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} f(p + q - s, s) ds.$$

Quyidagi belgilashlardan foydalanamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_1 &= \frac{1}{W_0} \quad va \quad W_0 = \int_{\mathbb{T}^3} \frac{\sin^2 s_1 ds}{\varepsilon(s)} \\ &\approx 0,2098. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

bu yerda W_0 integral Watson tipidagi integral deb ataladi. (q.[3]).

Bu ishning asosiy natijasini keltiramiz:

Teorema. $\lambda > 0$ bo'lsin. *i)* Agar $\gamma \in (0, \gamma_1)$ bo'lsa, u holda shunday $\mu(\gamma, \lambda) > 0$ son topiladiki barcha $\mu > \mu(\gamma, \lambda)$ lar uchun $H_{\mu, \lambda, \gamma}(\pi)$ operator muhim spektrdan chapda yotuvchi hech bo'lmaganda bitta xos qiymatga ega;

ii) Agar $\gamma \in (\gamma_1, +\infty)$ bo'lsa, u holda shunday $\mu(\gamma, \lambda) > 0$ son topiladiki barcha $\mu > \mu(\gamma, \lambda)$ lar uchun $H_{\mu, \lambda, \gamma}(\pi)$ operator muhim spektrdan chapda yotuvchi to'rttadan kam bo'lmagan xos qiymatga ega.

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